

Open Blockchain Platform : OpenchainGlobal:From community to enterprise, from platform to various application

Hans(Namkyu) Choi^a

^a *Chungbuk National University, South Korea*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Application & use of cases of blockchain.
Open blockchain platform supports
- multi platforms
. Multichain,
Ethereum,
Hyperledger
- multi programming languages.
. Java,
Golang,
Python,
PHP -
Multifields .
general
finance
& advanced
Fintech . P2P
Crowdfunding.
Cryptocurrency /
ICO Real estate,
Used car sales . Big data, Cloud computing, AI
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-multi platforms
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